

METHODS OF CHOOSING THE MATERIAL COMPOSITION AND JUSTIFYING THEM WHEN CREATING BEARING DETAILS.

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Annotation. Research has shown that the durability of bearings made of electroslag steel is 1.5 times higher than that of conventional electrical steel.

The effectiveness of vacuum treatment of steel was tested on bearings. At the same time, the following has been studied: Bearing durability increases by 2 - 2.5 times; defects on working surfaces are reduced several times.

Keywords: research, technological, material, shaft, hardness, content, vacuum, impact viscosity, bearing details, ring, casting method.

Introduction

Sliding and rolling bearing steels can be divided into two groups. High-carbon tempering: low-carbon steels (cementing) or carbon impregnation of the steel surface The bearings most commonly used in industry are produced from high-carbon steels by subsequent tempering and annealing at a certain temperature.

Material characteristics of bearing rings and rolling elements:

high bond strength in rolling;

high hardness;

high bending resistance;

high dimensional stability;

high mechanical strength.

Features of the materials used for the separator:

high bending resistance;

high dimensional stability;

high mechanical strength.

Material and Methods

Bearing steel ShX-15, which is currently the most widely used in mechanical engineering, has a chemical composition of 0.95-1.05 C according to GOST 801-78; 0.20-0.40% Mn; 0.17-0.37% Si; 1.30-1.60% Cr; 0.02-C; 0.027-% P; 0.30% Ni; 0.25% Cu; consists of elements.

Currently, in some cases, such steel is ShX-15SG; with an increase in the amount of manganese and silicon (0.9-1.20%) Mn; 0.4-0.6% Si steel is used with increased malleability.

Results

Since the bearings work in a very high voltage working environment, it is necessary to have a metal structure with the same structure and a very small amount of non-metallic particles, and carbides and martensite crystals are dispersed in the crushed particles of the structure.

So far, the demand of the time (GKM) (Horizontal hammering machine) in a wide variety of dimensions with high precision has not been satisfied with this machine. In addition, such machines are being produced less often in (GKM) production enterprises. It is related to high consumption of metal.

Discussion

The choice of bearing material brands depends on their wall thickness. In this case, depending on the field of use of the bearing, the stiffness measurement of the thickness of the walls was chosen.

Conclusion

In the research, the new proposed method is effective in obtaining bearing ring materials and manufacturing bearing details through the periodic casting method.

In the process of periodic casting, it was selected in order to meet the requirements and needs of small industries and based on local conditions. In this regard, it was selected based on the processes implemented in regional enterprises. Periodic casting is carried out in certain furnaces. Based on this, the quality of the material is scientifically based and applied in practice

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